

Participatory tools

SNOWBALL TECHNIQUE

INNOVATE TOGETHER DURING THE PROJECT PERIOD: WORKING TOGETHER

How do we organize our working together and decision making?

To ensure that working together and the decision-making process are shared and clear to all, the group validates them collectively. If possible, you can encourage collective decision-making and involve partners to keep them motivated (cf. Involve and maintain motivation).

A decision about collective work, if taken collectively, will be easier for the partners to accept. They will have had the opportunity to exchange, share their views, debate, and understand each other's pros and cons.

How to solve it

A clear and shared work plan is helpful. It defines the bases and needs to be clear, understood and shared by all. It helps everyone to be clear about what is expected and when.

Trust is the key. It comes from clarity and transparency. Your role is to create a climate of trust so that everyone can express themselves freely when making decisions.

Time is a necessary resource. You make sure to allow sufficient time to establish the decision rules for collective decision making.

It is a collective process where everyone is included in the decisions that affect them.

Words of advice

These are prerequisites to be put in place for good functioning throughout the project.

One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Snowball technique - The tree that synthesises the forest.

Description of the tool

- **What:** Dealing with an issue in a participatory way, in a large group, quickly
- **How long:** 30' to 60' according to group size
- **How many:** 8 to 40 approx.
- **What you'll need:** flip chart papers, markers

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

Steps:

- The facilitator formulates the question to be addressed and ensures that it is clear to all
- Alone: each person drafts their response to the question or issue raised
- In pairs: pooling of ideas and development of a consensus
- In groups of four: The same but between two pairs. The group of four writes its summary on a flip chart
- If necessary, carry out an additional accumulation stage before the flip chart exercise
- All: presentation of each summary for collective decision making

Tips:

- For a mature, self-regulating group
- Have space for people to connect
- Pace the time with a whistle
- Depending on the objective, creation, or choice, it takes different times

